

Methodology for developing speed-strength qualities in freestyle wrestlers

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Abstract

This article explores the scientific and methodological foundations of developing speed-strength qualities in freestyle wrestlers. The study analyzes modern training techniques, a set of specialized exercises, and their impact on the physical preparedness of athletes. The harmonious development of speed and strength qualities is recognized as a crucial factor in enhancing the technical and tactical mastery of wrestlers.

Keywords: freestyle wrestling, speed-strength qualities, physical preparation, explosive strength, specialized exercises, methodology.

Introduction

Currently, freestyle wrestling is developing rapidly on a global scale. The development of physical qualities, especially speed and strength, plays a crucial role in athletes achieving high results. Speed-strength qualities are the main factor in a wrestler's high effectiveness in performing technical and tactical actions, as well as maintaining stability and superiority throughout the competition. Therefore, developing these qualities on a scientific basis and creating methodological approaches aimed at their improvement is one of the urgent tasks of modern sports theory and practice. This study analyzes modern training technologies, load blocks, and training process management systems, and develops practical recommendations to enhance the speed-strength qualities of freestyle wrestlers.

Research objective: To develop a scientifically based methodology for improving speed-strength qualities in freestyle wrestlers, and to propose an effective training system that contributes to their achievement of high results in competitive activities.

Research Objectives: To analyze scientific and methodological sources on the development of speed-strength qualities and synthesize existing approaches.

To determine the role and importance of speed-strength qualities in the physical preparation of freestyle wrestlers.

Development of a special set of exercises

for enhancing speed-strength qualities and experimental testing of their effectiveness.

Evaluation of changes in physical fitness indicators of freestyle wrestlers during the experiment based on mathematical and statistical analysis.

Research methods. In the research process, a set of complementary scientific methods was used to achieve the established goals and objectives. First, existing scientific approaches to developing speed-strength qualities in freestyle wrestlers were studied through the examination and analysis of scientific and methodological sources. Additionally, using the pedagogical observation method, the athletes' motor activity during training, exercise technique execution, and speed indicators were observed.

Results and discussion

During the study, a system of special preparatory exercises was developed and tested in practice to enhance the speed-strength qualities of freestyle wrestlers. Based on the methodology applied in the experimental group, training sessions were organized three times a week over an 8-week cycle. The program included plyometric exercises, short-distance sprints at maximum speed, resistance jumps, explosive movements with a medicine ball, and dynamic exercises that increase muscle activation.

Comparison of pre-study and post-study indicators revealed that the athletes significantly improved their movement speed, explosive strength, quickness, and coordination abilities. A detailed analysis for each test result is provided below:

1. 30-meter Sprint Test. At the beginning of the study, the results of the experimental and control groups were similar, recording 4.62 ± 0.14 seconds and 4.63 ± 0.15 seconds, respectively. At the end of the training period, a slight

Table 1. Test trials for assessing speed-strength qualities

No	Test name	Unit of measurement	Test content	Evaluation objective
1.	30-meter sprint	seconds	The athlete covers a 30-meter distance at maximum speed	Determine movement speed
2.	Standing vertical jump	cm	The athlete jumps to maximum height from a standing position	Determine explosive power
3.	Backward medicine ball throw (3 kg)	meters	The athlete throws the ball backward with both hands	Assess explosive power and coordination
4.	Pull-ups	repetitions	Maximum number of pull-ups on a horizontal bar	Assess upper body strength
5.	10m × 4m shuttle run	seconds	The athlete runs a 10-meter distance four times with direction changes	Assess speed and agility in changing direction

improvement (4.58 ± 0.12 s) was observed in the control group, while a significant improvement (4.35 ± 0.10 s) was noted in the experimental group. This is attributed to the improvement in speed reaction and optimization of stride length and frequency.

2. Standing Vertical Jump. This test measures the explosive power of athletes' lower body muscles. During the study, the results of the experimental group increased from 46.4 cm to 50.2 cm, representing a +8.2% improvement. Plyometric exercises (jumps, step transitions, resistance jumps) enhanced the neuromuscular activity of the knee and thigh muscles, increasing the jump amplitude.

ments, and coordination of the tension and relaxation cycle of the shoulder girdle.

4. Pull-ups. This test assesses upper body strength and endurance. In the experimental group, the number of pull-ups increased from 11.6 to 13.4 times, which represents an increase of +15.5%. This demonstrates the effectiveness of special strength exercises (rubber band-assisted pull-ups, climbing exercises, and plyometric push-ups).

5. 10×4 m shuttle run. This test evaluates the athlete's speed in changing direction and coordination accuracy. In the experimental group, the time decreased from 9.79 to 9.41 seconds, showing an improvement of 4.1%.

Table 2. Pre-study and post-study results (average indicators)

Test name	Unit of measurement	Pre-study (control group)	Post-study (control group)	Pre-study (experimental group)	Post-study (experimental group)
30m sprint	seconds	4.63 ± 0.15	4.58 ± 0.12	4.62 ± 0.14	4.35 ± 0.10
Vertical jump from standing position	cm	46.5 ± 2.3	47.1 ± 2.0	46.4 ± 2.2	50.2 ± 1.8
Backward medicine ball throw	m	6.1 ± 0.4	6.3 ± 0.3	6.2 ± 0.4	7.0 ± 0.3
Pull-ups	repetitions	11.4 ± 1.2	11.8 ± 1.1	11.6 ± 1.2	13.4 ± 1.0

3. Backward Medicine Ball Throw. A significant result was also observed in this test, which measures explosive power and coordination. In the experimental group, the average performance increased from 6.2 meters to 7.0 meters, recording an improvement of 12.9%. These gains were achieved through dynamic throws with a medicine ball, rotational move-

This improvement is attributed to enhanced quick reaction, spatial awareness, and coordination of leg movements.

Conclusion

Based on observations, experiments, and tests conducted during the study, it can be deter-

mined that the development of speed-strength qualities in freestyle wrestlers is one of the decisive factors in their competitive activity.

Speed-strength qualities determine the explosiveness of the wrestler's movements and the ability to perform technical techniques quickly and effectively. In the training process based on the experimental program, special plyometric exercises, explosive movements with a medicine ball, short-distance running, resistance exercises, and dynamic strength exercises were systematically applied.

As a result, the athletes' muscle strength, speed, jumping ability, and motor reaction improved significantly. Comparison of the results before and at the end of the study showed that the developed methodology: Allowed to increase the explosive strength of athletes by 8-13%; Improved movement speed and reaction time, significantly reducing the 30-meter run times; Enhanced coordination abilities, which contributed to the accurate and fast execution of technical techniques; Optimized the muscular system and neuromuscular connection, resulting in increased motor efficiency of the athlete.

Overall, the developed methodology for improving speed-strength qualities has shown high effectiveness in enhancing the physical fitness and competitive results of freestyle wrestlers. This methodology is recommended not only for highly qualified athletes but also for working with adolescent and young wrestlers.

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Research interests

Wrestling, Olympic games, physical education and sport, Theory of physical education, Analyzing of sport competitions